

Author's Accepted Manuscript

Magnetic studies of polystyrene/iron-filled multi-wall carbon nanotube composite films

T.L. Makarova, I. Zakharchuk, P. Geydt, E. Lahderanta, A.A. Komlev, A.A. Zyrianova, M.A. Kanygin, O.V. Sedelnikova, V.I. Suslyayev, L.G. Bulusheva, A.V. Okotrub

PII: S0304-8853(16)30088-9
DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.jmmm.2016.01.088>
Reference: MAGMA61112

To appear in: *Journal of Magnetism and Magnetic Materials*

Received date: 13 August 2015
Revised date: 18 November 2015
Accepted date: 26 January 2016

Cite this article as: T.L. Makarova, I. Zakharchuk, P. Geydt, E. Lahderanta, A.A. Komlev, A.A. Zyrianova, M.A. Kanygin, O.V. Sedelnikova, V.I. Suslyayev, L.G. Bulusheva and A.V. Okotrub, Magnetic studies of polystyrene/iron-filled multi-wall carbon nanotube composite films, *Journal of Magnetism and Magnetic Materials*, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.jmmm.2016.01.088>

This is a PDF file of an unedited manuscript that has been accepted for publication. As a service to our customers we are providing this early version of the manuscript. The manuscript will undergo copyediting, typesetting, and a review of the resulting galley proof before it is published in its final citable form. Please note that during the production process errors may be discovered which could affect the content, and all legal disclaimers that apply to the journal pertain

Magnetic studies of polystyrene/iron-filled multi-wall carbon nanotube composite films

T. L. Makarova^{1,2}, I. Zakharchuk¹, P. Geydt¹, E. Lahderanta¹, A. A. Komlev³, A. A. Zyrianova², M. A. Kanygin⁴, O. V. Sedelnikova,^{4,5} V. I. Suslyayev⁶, L. G. Bulusheva^{4,5}, A. V. Okotrub^{4,5}

¹*Lappeenranta University of Technology, FI-53851 Lappeenranta, Finland*

²*Ioffe Institute, St Petersburg 194021, Russia*

³*St Petersburg State Electrotechnical University, St Petersburg 197376, Russia*

⁴*Nikolaev Institute of Inorganic Chemistry, SB RAS, Novosibirsk 630090, Russia*

⁵*Novosibirsk State University, Novosibirsk 630090, Russia*

⁶*Tomsk State University, Tomsk 634050, Russia*

*Corresponding author. Tel: +358417020501. E-mail: Tatyana.makarova@lut.fi (Tatiana Makarova)

Abstract

Polystyrene / iron-filled multi-wall carbon nanotube composite films were prepared by solution processing, forge-rolling and stretching methods. Elongated iron carbide nanoparticles formed because of catalytic growth are situated inside the hollow cavity of the nanotubes. Magnetic susceptibility measurements as well as records of isothermal hysteresis loops performed in three perpendicular directions of magnetic field confirmed that the nanotubes have a preferential alignment in the matrix. Strong diamagnetic anisotropy in the composites emerges not only from the MWCNTs but also from the polystyrene matrix. The polymer sticks to the honeycomb lattice through the interaction of the π -orbitals of the phenyl ring and those of the carbon nanotube, contributing to anisotropic diamagnetic response. The contribution of iron nanoparticles to overall magnetic response strongly depends on nanotube concentration in the composite as well as on matrix-filler non-covalent stacking, which influences magnetic interparticle interactions.

Keywords: polystyrene, multi-wall carbon nanotubes, iron nanoparticles, composite, magnetization, anisotropic susceptibility.

1. Introduction

Carbon nanotubes (CNTs) are ideal fillers for composites used in many practical areas as light-weight structures with multifunctional properties for engineering applications. Composites with aligned nanotubes are very attractive for conductive applications or for electromagnetic shielding, used in military and biomedical applications to prevent the interaction of electromagnetic fields and biological tissues. CNT composites are highly attractive in shielding due to their low cost, high strength, and simple processing. It was shown that the better the orientation, the higher the polymer composites' mechanical strength and shielding effectiveness. Electromagnetic properties of polymer composites can be improved by controlling the orientation of MWCNTs, which results in an anisotropic response of polymer composite relative to low frequency [1] and terahertz radiation [2]. The magnetic catalytic particles embedded into the carbon nanotubes during the synthesis can lead to novel magnetic properties of the nonmagnetic polymer matrix. Recent experiments and simulations investigated the role of catalytic particles in composite properties: shielding effectiveness of composites with iron-filled nanotubes is higher than that for purified nanotubes, without contribution from the nanotube-enclosed metal catalysts. The explanation is not trivial because carbon nanotubes constitute about 1% in the composites, and iron nanoparticles, in turn, constitute several per cent of nanotube weight. Therefore, the effect was thought of being due to the contributions of magnetic losses and impedance match. Alternatively, the effect was attributed to increased dielectric losses because the magnetic particles content is so small that the magnetic effects are weak. Here we show that the properties of iron-based nanoparticles inside the composite strongly differ from the properties of the same nanoparticles in freestanding nanotubes: we identified signs of magnetic interactions between iron and the carbon walls,

as well as magnetic interparticle interactions, presumably mediated by the extended intermolecular stacking.

The alignment of CNTs is mostly evaluated by the microscopy techniques like atomic force microscopy (AFM) and transmission electron microscopy (TEM) which provide surface information or spectroscopic techniques including polarized Raman spectroscopy. In this work, magnetic susceptibility measurements were used to evaluate iron-filled multi-wall CNTs (MWCNTs) orientation in polystyrene matrix, as well as to evaluate interface interactions. The measurements of magnetic moment versus field and versus temperature performed in three orthogonal directions of magnetic field produced valuable information about the orientation of MWCNTs, the arrangement of the macromolecules around them and the behaviour of catalyst nanoparticles. Comparison of the properties of anisotropic composites prepared by different methods showed that the samples with strongly anisotropic diamagnetic properties provide anisotropic electromagnetic response and show high shielding efficiency in gigahertz range.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. MWCNT synthesis

Arrays of MWCNTs on silicon substrates were produced using aerosol-assisted catalytic chemical vapour deposition method, which is described in detail elsewhere [3]. Synthesis was carried out in a quartz tube inserting into a horizontal tubular reactor. Silicon substrates with a size of $10 \times 10 \text{ mm}^2$ were located in the central part of the reactor, then the reactor was pumped, filled with argon gas and heated up to 800°C . Ferrocene (2 wt. %) was dissolved in toluene and the reaction mixture was injected into the reactor with a rate of 0.14 ml/min. The pyrolysis was performed at atmospheric pressure in an argon flow ($250 \text{ cm}^3/\text{min}$) for an hour. Concentration of iron nanoparticles in the nanotube channels determined by elemental analysis was 3 wt. %.

2.2 Composite preparation

Polystyrene plates with 1 - 5 wt. % MWCNT loading were prepared using forge-rolling and stretching methods [4]. MWCNT array (so-called nanotube forest) was gently detached from silicon substrate; a required amount of MWCNTs separated from the silicon substrate was put into a toluene solution of polystyrene and the mixture was mechanically stirred until complete polymer dissolving. Then, the suspension was sonicated for ~2 min using a high-power sonic tip (200 W) with the purpose to improve the MWCNT dispersion. As produced slush was cast onto metallic substrate and dried to a viscous state at ambient conditions. The plate produced after complete solvent evaporation contains randomly distributed nanotubes. To provide predominant orientation of nanotubes in polymer matrix we used a procedure of forge-rolling or stretching.

In the first batch of samples, a forge-rolling procedure was used. A composite plate was repeatedly forge-rolled along a certain direction at a linear speed of the rolls of ~ 10–15 cm/s. In the second batch, a stretching procedure was used. A soft composite plate was uniaxially stretched at a heating (~70°C), which was provided by a hot air gun. A microscrew setup led to stretching of the plate in half. Finally, the composites were dried under a light load at room temperature. All the prepared plates had visually homogeneous grey colour. Investigation of the electromagnetic response of the composites prepared by the above-described techniques detected that the nanotubes have a predominant orientation in the plates [5].

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Electron microscopy and atomic force microscopy.

For transmission electron microscopy (TEM) investigation, the MWCNTs were mixed with ethanol and after ultrasonication; the suspension was deposited on colloidal carbon film grid. TEM images obtained on a Jeol JEM 2010

microscope showed that the CCVD product consists of MWCNTs with an outer diameter of ~ 20 nm (Fig. 1 a). Dark-contrast nanoparticles observed on the TEM images correspond to metallic compounds produced from ferrocene $\text{Fe}(\text{C}_5\text{H}_5)_2$. The catalytic nanoparticles are elongated with average diameter 5 – 10 nm and length of 10 – 20 nm and are captured in the interior cavity of nanotubes (Fig. 2b). Mössbauer spectroscopy study of MWCNTs synthesized by the same method detected three forms of iron nanoparticles, namely, two magnetic phases α -Fe and Fe_3C and one non-magnetic γ -Fe phase [6]. From the results obtained after the sample treatment with a diluted sulfuric acid, it was supposed that the α -Fe phase is mainly located close to the nanotube ends, while the γ -Fe and Fe_3C phases are inside of the channels [7].

SEM images of the composites obtained from a Jeol JSM-7001F microscope confirm that the processing conditions ensure a good dispersion of the MWCNTs in the polystyrene (Fig. 1 c). Atomic force microscopy (AFM) show that MWCNTs are embedded into the polystyrene matrix, and only in rare exceptions are lying on the surface (Fig. 1d).

3.2. Thermomagnetic measurements

Measurements were done using a superconducting quantum interference device (SQUID) magnetometer. Magnetic properties of samples were studied by measuring the zero field cooled (ZFC) and field cooled (FC) magnetizations at $H = 100$ Oe as a function of temperature and isothermal magnetic hysteresis loops, $M(H)$, at a given temperature. The magnetic field was varied in the range -5 T to 5 T, within the temperature range 2 – 400 K. The magnetic moment was measured with the sensitivity of 10^{-8} electromagnetic units (emu).

Figure 2 summarises the results of magnetic measurements on pristine MWCNT forest and the composite materials. Fig. 2a plots the coercive force values, extracted from isothermal magnetization loops measured parallel and perpendicular to the nanotube axis. There is distinct anisotropy in magnetostatic

parameters extracted from the isothermal magnetization loops which is apparently due to the iron particles inside the nanotubes. For a rod-like shape ferromagnetic material, the demagnetizing factor is zero when the field is parallel to the axis and increases up to 2π when the field is perpendicular to the rod axis, which results in a nonsquare hysteresis loop. This anisotropy confirms that the easy axis is parallel to the nanotube axis and that the nanotubes are well aligned both in the forest and in the composites.

Figures 2 b – 2 f present the results of magnetic moment measurements performed in ZFC and FC protocols. Fig. 2b shows the plot for raw MWCNT forest, 2c for the composite prepared by forge-rolled method, and 2d – f are the plots for the stretched composites with different MWCNT load.

The results in Fig. 2 a – 2f, namely, increased coercive force and the difference between the ZFC and FC protocols, in a first approximation can be described by the Stoner and Wohlfarth model which accounts for the non-interacting single-domain particles with uniaxial anisotropy resulting from shape or from the magnetocrystalline anisotropy in the assumption of coherent rotation of the magnetization. Isothermal field dependencies for the nanotube forest indicate difference between the coercive fields for in-plane field orientation compared to that for out-of-plane orientation. The obtained coercivities are larger than those for bulk Fe_3C that does not exceed 100 Oe at room temperature. For the nanotube forest, the room temperature in-plane coercivity is 425 Oe whereas the out-of-plane coercivity is 500 Oe. The squariness, i.e. the ratio of remnant to saturation magnetization (M_R / M_S) is around 0.43 and 0.45 correspondingly. This is the indication of the size effect: coercivities of single domain particles are much larger than those of bulk materials. Temperature dependence of coercivity for such particles follows the law

$$H_c(T) / H_c(0) = 1 - (T/T_B)^n \quad (1)$$

where T_B is the blocking temperature for the largest particles in the system and the exponent n equals 0.5 in the Stoner and Wohlfarth model. Our experiments are not described by this model, but are perfectly fitted by the exponent $n = 0.77$ which indicates (a) distribution of easy axis [8] and (b) random assemblies where not only irreversible (switching) processes, but also reversible (rotational) processes determine the magnetization curve [9]. The blocking temperature estimated from Eq. (1) is about 500 K. Another formula, which estimates the blocking temperature, links the anisotropy constant and particle volume:

$$T_B \sim V K / k_B \quad (2)$$

where $V \sim d^2 l$ is the average volume of the nanoparticles (d – diameter, about 5-10 nm, l is average length, about 10-20 nm), K is the anisotropy constant (for bulk iron carbide $K = 0.394 \cdot 10^5$ erg/cm³). Substituting the averaged values into Eq. (2) gives $T_B = 300$ K. This is a clear underestimation because for nanoparticles the values of local magnetic anisotropy K can be several times higher. Therefore, the value of the blocking temperature determined from the extrapolation of coercive force to zero seems reasonable.

The 0.77 law of Eq. 1 remains valid for both composites (Fig. 2a). However, in the forge-rolled composite the anisotropy towards magnetic field direction nearly disappears. In the stretched composite the difference between the coercive forces in orthogonal direction is preserved, and, strikingly, the values of coercive force are strongly increased compared to the nanotube forest. For both directions, there is surprisingly high difference of approximately 40% between the coercive force of the embedded nanotubes and the nanotube forest. This effect should be attributed to the exchange interaction between the ferromagnetic core of the nanoparticle and the carbon shell. This interaction has the effect of the enhanced interface anisotropy, which causes a considerable increase in the coercive field of the nanoparticles.

Further information about the interactions of catalytic particle with the nanotubes and with the matrix was obtained from temperature dependencies of magnetic moment. Strong difference between zero field cooled and field cooled measurements confirms the superparamagnetic behaviour of iron nanoparticles inside the MWCNTs (Fig. 2b). Superparamagnetic features are preserved in the forge-rolled composites with the 5% load (Fig. 2c). However, they are not observed in the stretched composites with the 5% load (Fig. 2f). To get further insight into this phenomenon, we performed measurements on stretched composites with the 1% and 2.5% MWCNT load (Fig. 2d, e correspondingly). Superparamagnetic behaviour is observed in the 1% composite, but the composite with 2.5% MWCNTs demonstrate clear superparamagnetic features only for the in-plane but not for out-of-plane measurements. In the measurements on individual non-interacting nanoparticles, the increase of magnetic moment in the ZFC measurements is associated with the rotation of magnetic moment of each nanoparticle lying along the magnetic easy axis and energetically degenerate with respect of the parallel and antiparallel direction. This is observed on MWCNT forest, forge-rolled composites and stretched composites with small MWCNT load. However, in stretched composites with 5% load the increase of magnetic moment in ZFC measurements is not observed any more (Fig. 2f), i.e. isolated iron carbide nanoparticles with concentration about 0.15% of the composite weight show the features of ferromagnetic phase, and specifically the temperature run resembles the dependence of the spontaneous magnetization below T_c for the ferromagnet.

It was suggested that an indirect exchange coupling between magnetic nanoparticles in carbon nanotube media could be of great importance for determining the entire magnetic properties [10 - 12]. Our results confirm the understanding that magnetic properties of nanoparticles inside carbon nanotubes are influenced by the nanotubes. Additionally, we demonstrate that they are

influenced by the MWCNT arrangement in an organic matrix where they are embedded: in further discussion, we will show the difference between the mutual arrangement of the filler and the matrix for the forge-rolled and stretched methods. In this section, we emphasize that iron-filled carbon nanotubes in an organic matrix should be regarded as a 3-component mutually interfering magnetic system.

3.3. Diamagnetic susceptibility

Although it is clearly seen from Fig. 2 that magnetic susceptibility of MWCNT forest and MWCNT composites is anisotropic, the thermomagnetic measurements do not allow assessing intrinsic magnetic properties of either nanotubes or polystyrene matrix. Ferromagnetic catalyst particles provide increased magnetization in low magnetic fields due to the contribution from initial magnetic susceptibility. We used the field dependencies of magnetization, $M(H)$ curves, taken at different temperatures and at orthogonal directions of magnetic field. Figure 3 a, b shows room temperature loops. The loops are similar for the measurements at 50 – 300 K, but below 50 K the measurements of diamagnetic contribution are not reliable due to contribution from Curie paramagnetism. The response from catalytic nanoparticles saturates at 1 T and we estimated the diamagnetic contribution from a linear diamagnetic portion of the $M(H)$ curve above 2 T. The parameter that we are interested in this section is

$$\Delta\chi = \chi_{\perp} - \chi_{\parallel} \quad (3)$$

where χ_{\perp} and χ_{\parallel} are the values of diamagnetic susceptibility for the magnetic field perpendicular and parallel to the nanotube axis.

Comparison of Fig. 3a and 3b reveals that the stretched composites show much larger anisotropy of diamagnetic susceptibility compared to the forge-rolled ones. Indeed the value $\Delta\chi$ is about $-0.6 \cdot 10^{-6}$ and for the forge-rolled one it four times less $-0.14 \cdot 10^{-6}$. If all the nanotubes were aligned the theoretical value $\Delta\chi$ of a composite with for 5% MWCNT loading will not exceed $-0.20 \cdot 10^{-6}$. This can be considered as an upper bound, because magnetic susceptibility of CNTs is determined by its diameter, and the diameters are diverse (see Fig. 1a). For the forge-rolled samples, the $\Delta\chi$ value matches well the theoretical predictions if about 80% of MWCNTs are aligned. For the stretched composites the value $\Delta\chi = -0.6 \cdot 10^{-6}$ exceeds the theoretically possible one. The only plausible explanation that the nanotubes are wrapped with the polystyrene macromolecules. Driven by the aromatic interactions, the phenyl rings of polystyrene turn parallel to the nanotube (Fig. 3c) and contribute to an additional anisotropy.

4. Discussion

Diamagnetic properties of MWCNT / polystyrene matrix are determined by (i) MWCNTs (ii) polystyrene matrix and (iii) interface interactions between the two components. CNTs have anisotropic diamagnetic susceptibility [13]. Atactic polystyrene is an amorphous polymer with a phenyl side group per repeat unit, is a magnetically isotropic material with diamagnetic susceptibility $\chi = -0.53 \cdot 10^{-6}$ emu/g Oe. However, polystyrene contains aromatic phenyl rings, and spatial arrangement of polymer chains may turn this material to strongly anisotropic because magnetic field induces large currents in the aromatic ring. The value for the anisotropy of the diamagnetic susceptibility for the benzene equals to $-1.11 \cdot 10^{-28}$ emu/molecule [14] which in case of fully oriented rings will result in anisotropic diamagnetic susceptibility $\Delta\chi = -0.86 \cdot 10^{-6}$ emu/g Oe.

Strong interfacial interactions between aromatic polymers and single-wall CNTs are governed by their mutual arrangement: they are maximized when the polystyrene macromolecule is stretched along the nanotube [15]. An experimental study also revealed that stretching orientation is a highly efficacious pathway to achieve interfacial enhancement in between polystyrene and MWCNTs [16]. Our measurements of anisotropic diamagnetic susceptibility correlate well with the fact that a considerable increase in the diamagnetic susceptibility and high anisotropy are typical for delocalized cyclic compounds. Figures 3 c, d illustrate the initial stages of the composite formation. Aromatic ring systems interact strongly with carbon nanotubes, presumably due to the polarizable π -systems on both the aromatic functional groups and the nanotube. In the stretching procedure, the macromolecules have a good contact with the nanotube, and the aromatic rings are approximately parallel to the surface. The neighbouring rings in polystyrene occupy the places on the nanotube surface thus wrapping the nanotube and initiating wrapping of other molecules (Fig. 3c). In case of the disordered system formed during forge-rolling, (Fig. 3d) the macromolecules are crumpled, so the intermolecular interactions with the nanotubes are less effective.

Forge-rolled and stretched nanotubes proved to be very different in their electromagnetic properties. The most important variables, which impact on electromagnetic response of composite, are the MWCNTs ordering state, their length l , and defectiveness; transmission and reflection of the composite are strongly dependent on orientation of the plate in respect to the polarization of electromagnetic wave [5]. The samples (MWCNTs and composites) have been prepared using the above-described techniques, but the MWCNT loading in composites was 0.25 wt. %. Microwave response of the polystyrene/MWCNT composites was examined by a vector network analyser Agilent N5247A. The forge-rolled composite has a negligible difference in microwave transmission

and absorption for parallel and perpendicular orientations of the plate relative to polarization of the electric field. The stretched composite showed noticeable dependence of the transmission (40% versus 55%) and in absorption (60% versus 37%) for two electric field polarizations. Hence, we should conclude that alignment of MWCNTs in polymer matrix is strongly correlated with the transmission/reflection THz spectra taken at different orientation of sample in respect to the electric field.

5. Conclusion

We have performed a study of magnetic properties of catalytically grown MWCNTs inside polystyrene matrix and paid attention to different preparation methods and different nanotube content. The largest contribution to the measured magnetic moment comes from catalytic iron nanoparticles situated in the inner cavities of the nanotubes in the form of iron carbides. In the raw MWCNT the iron content is 3 wt. % and therefore in the studied composites it ranges from 0.03 to 0.15 wt. %. We identified the individual contributions of nanotubes, matrix and iron nanoparticles in the total magnetic response and showed their mutual interference. Therefore, iron-filled carbon nanotubes in an organic matrix should be regarded as a 3-component interacting magnetic system. Fabrication method influences the arrangement of nanotubes in polystyrene matrix and their interfacial interactions with the macromolecules. Diamagnetic susceptibility of composites measured parallel and perpendicular to the nanotube axis showed that for the stretched samples anisotropy was stronger than expected from the nanotubes. The findings are explained from the point of view of interfacial interactions. The aromatic rings of polystyrene stick to the honeycomb nanotubes, wrap them, and coat them. This process is effective in the stretching procedure but not in a forge-rolled one, confirming the theoretical predictions that stretching enhances interfacial interactions.

Superparamagnetic properties of iron-based catalyst nanoparticles encapsulated in the MWCNT cavities are modified in the coated nanotubes compared to the naked nanotubes, thus confirming the theoretical predictions about the exchange interactions between carbon and magnetic metals.

References

- [1] A. Okotrub, V. Kubarev, M. Kanygin, O. Sedelnikova, L. Bulusheva, Transmission of terahertz radiation by anisotropic MWCNT/polystyrene composite films, *physica status solidi (b)*. 248 (2011) 2568-2571.
- [2] M. Kanygin, A. Selyutin, A. Okotrub, L. Bulusheva, Anisotropic permittivity of multi-walled carbon nanotube/polystyrene composites, *Fullerenes, Nanotubes and Carbon Nanostructures*. 20 (2012) 523-526.
- [3] A. Kudashov, A. Kurennya, A. Okotrub, A. Gusel'nikov, V. Danilovich, L. Bulusheva, Synthesis and structure of films consisting of carbon nanotubes oriented normally to the substrate, *Technical Physics*. 52 (2007) 1627-1631.
- [4] O. Sedelnikova, M. Kanygin, E.Y. Korovin, L. Bulusheva, V. Suslyaev, A. Okotrub, Effect of fabrication method on the structure and electromagnetic response of carbon nanotube/polystyrene composites in low-frequency and K a bands, *Composites Sci. Technol*. 102 (2014) 59-64.
- [5] D. Bychanok, M. Shuba, P. Kuzhir, S. Maksimenko, V. Kubarev, M. Kanygin, O. Sedelnikova, L. Bulusheva, A. Okotrub, Anisotropic electromagnetic properties of polymer composites containing oriented multiwall carbon nanotubes in respect to terahertz polarizer applications, *J. Appl. Phys*. 114 (2013) 114304.
- [6] I. Lyubutin, O. Anosova, K. Frolov, S. Sulyanov, A. Okotrub, A. Kudashov, L. Bulusheva, Iron nanoparticles in aligned arrays of pure and nitrogen-doped carbon nanotubes, *Carbon*. 50 (2012) 2628-2634.
- [7] E. Fedorovskaya, L. Bulusheva, A. Kurennya, I. Asanov, N. Rudina, K. Funtov, I. Lyubutin, A. Okotrub, Supercapacitor performance of vertically aligned multiwall carbon nanotubes produced by aerosol-assisted CCVD method, *Electrochim. Acta*. 139 (2014) 165-172.

- [8] J. Harrell, Orientation dependence of the dynamic coercivity of Stoner-Wohlfarth particles, *Magnetics, IEEE Transactions on.* 37 (2001) 533-537.
- [9] H. Pfeiffer, Determination of anisotropy field distribution in particle assemblies taking into account thermal fluctuations, *physica status solidi (a)*. 118 (1990) 295-306.
- [10] A. Costa Jr, D. Kirwan, M. Ferreira, Indirect exchange coupling between magnetic adatoms in carbon nanotubes, *Physical Review B.* 72 (2005) 085402.
- [11] A. Danilyuk, I. Komissarov, V. Labunov, F. Le Normand, A. Derory, J. Hernandez, J. Tejada, S. Prischepa, Manifestation of coherent magnetic anisotropy in a carbon nanotube matrix with low ferromagnetic nanoparticle content, *New Journal of Physics.* 17 (2015) 023073.
- [12] P. Gorman, J. Duffy, S. Power, M. Ferreira, Strain-modified RKKY interaction in carbon nanotubes, *Physical Review B.* 92 (2015) 035411.
- [13] Y. Nakai, R. Tsukada, Y. Miyata, T. Saito, K. Hata, Y. Maniwa, Observation of the intrinsic magnetic susceptibility of highly purified single-wall carbon nanotubes, *Physical Review B.* 92 (2015) 041402.
- [14] A. Bothner-By, C. Gayathri, P. Van Zijl, C. Maclean, Anisotropy of the diamagnetic susceptibility of benzene. Determination by high-field deuterium NMR, *Journal of Magnetic Resonance* (1969). 56 (1984) 456-462.
- [15] B. Yu, S. Fu, Z. Wu, H. Bai, N. Ning, Q. Fu, Molecular dynamics simulations of orientation induced interfacial enhancement between single walled carbon nanotube and aromatic polymers chains, *Composites Part A: Applied Science and Manufacturing.* 73 (2015) 155-165.
- [16] K. Wang, N. Li, K. Ren, Q. Zhang, Q. Fu, Exploring interfacial enhancement in polystyrene/multiwalled carbon nanotube monofilament induced by stretching, *Composites Part A: Applied Science and Manufacturing.* 61 (2014) 84-90.

Figure captions|

Figure 1. HRTEM images of MWCNTs from the array (a. b). SEM image of the MWCNT-polystyrene composite (c). AFM 3D topography image of the MWCNT-polystyrene composite (d).

Figure 2. Values of coercive force for the nanotube forest, forge-rolled and stretched composites with magnetic field perpendicular (\perp) and parallel (\parallel) to the nanotube axis (a). Temperature dependencies of magnetic susceptibility measured in ZFC and FC regimes with magnetic field perpendicular (\perp) and parallel (\parallel) to the nanotube axis for pristine nanotube forest (b), forge-rolled (c) and stretched (d-f) composites.

Figure 3. Room-temperature $M(H)$ curves for the stretched (a) and forge-rolled (b) composites. Symbols " \parallel " and " \perp " in (a, b) indicate orientation of MWCNTs in polystyrene matrix relative to the magnetic field. Models explaining differences in diamagnetic susceptibility of the stretched (c) and forge-rolled (d) composites.

Acknowledgments: This work was supported by European FP7 IRSES project 295180 MagNonMag and Horizon2020-RISE project 691010 Hunter. This work was partially supported by the Russian Scientific Foundation (Grant #15-13-20021) We thank A.G. Kurenya for the MWCNT samples and E.Yu. Korovin for the microwave measurements.

Highlights

- Multi-wall carbon nanotubes/polystyrene composites were prepared by stretching and forge-rolling methods.

- Strong contribution to the anisotropic diamagnetic response of the composites comes from the phenyl aromatic rings wrapping the nanotubes.
- Iron-based nanoparticles elongated in the nanotube cavity display different magnetic behaviour, depending upon nanotube concentration in the composite as well as stacking interactions with the matrix.
- Interactions between iron carbide nanoparticles and organic shells provide a source for interface anisotropy.
- Magnetic susceptibility measurements is a penetrative and non-destructive tool for assessment both carbon nanotube orientation and their non-covalent interactions with the organic matrix.

Figure 1

